

Permuting Sparse Square Matrices into Block Diagonal Form with Overlap

Seher Acer^a, Enver Kayaaslan^a, Tugrul Dayar^a, Cevdet Aykanat^a

^a*Bilkent University, Computer Engineering Department, 06800 Ankara, Turkey*

Abstract

In this whitepaper, we describe the problem of permuting sparse square matrices into block diagonal form with overlap (BDO) and propose a graph partitioning algorithm for solving this problem. A block diagonal matrix with overlap is a block diagonal matrix whose consecutive diagonal blocks may overlap. The objective in this permutation problem is to minimize the total overlap size, whereas the permutation constraint is to maintain balance on the number of nonzeros in the diagonal blocks. This permutation problem arises in the parallelization of an explicit formulation of multiplicative Schwarz preconditioner. We define ordered Graph Partitioning by Vertex Separator (oGPVS) problem as an equivalent problem to this permutation problem. oGPVS problem is a restricted version of Graph Partitioning by Vertex Separator (GPVS) problem and the aim is to find a partition of the vertices into K ordered vertex parts and $K-1$ ordered separators where each two consecutive parts can be connected through only a separator, a separator can only connect two consecutive parts, and each two consecutive separators can be adjacent. The objective in the oGPVS problem is to minimize the total number of vertices in the separators, whereas the partitioning objective is to maintain balance on the part weights where part weight is defined as the sum of the weights of vertices in that part. To solve oGPVS problem, we utilized recursive bipartitioning paradigm and fixed vertices in our proposed oGPVS algorithm. We tested the performance of our algorithm in a wide range of matrices in comparison to another graph partitioning algorithm that solves the same problem. Results showed that the oGPVS algorithm performs better than the other algorithm in terms of overlap size.

1. Introduction

In this work, our target problem is to symmetrically permute the rows and columns of a given sparse square matrix into block diagonal form with overlap (BDO). BDO form contains K square diagonal blocks D_1, D_2, \dots, D_K where D_i and D_{i+1} may overlap, for $i=1, \dots, K-1$. In this permutation problem, the permutation objective is to minimize the overlap size, i.e., the total number of rows/columns in the overlapping regions. The permutation constraint is to maintain balance on the number of nonzeros in diagonal blocks D_i , for $i=1, \dots, K$.

The problem of permuting a sparse square matrix into BDO form arises in the parallelization of a multiplicative Schwarz preconditioner [1]. In this parallelization, each diagonal block D_i and its associated computations are

assigned to processor p_i . The permutation objective of minimizing the total overlap size corresponds to minimizing the total communication volume and minimizing an upper bound on the number iterations for convergence of the iterative solver [1, 2]. The permutation constraint of maintaining balance on the number of nonzeros of diagonal blocks relates to maintaining balance on the computational workloads of the processors [1].

The achievements reported in this whitepaper can be listed as follows:

- The problem of permuting a sparse square matrix into BDO form is defined.
- The ordered Graph Partitioning by Vertex Separator (oGPVS) problem is defined as an equivalent problem to this permutation problem.
- A recursive graph bipartitioning algorithm that utilizes fixed vertices is proposed to solve the oGPVS problem.
- Results of the oGPVS algorithm in comparison to a baseline algorithm [3] are given in terms of total overlap size and load imbalance.

2. Work Done

We formulate the problem of permuting a sparse square matrix into BDO form as a graph partitioning problem, which we name as *ordered Graph Partitioning by Vertex Separator* (oGPVS) problem. The oGPVS problem is a restricted version of Graph Partitioning by Vertex Separator (GPVS) problem. In GPVS problem, the aim is to find a partition of the vertices of a given graph into K vertex parts and one separator such that the removal of the separator vertices disconnects the graph into at least K components. The restriction of the oGPVS problem is that the overall separator consists of $K-1$ ordered separators such that each separator is confined to be between two consecutive vertex parts provided that the vertex parts are also ordered. Then, only consecutive vertex part pairs can be connected and they are connected through a vertex separator, and only consecutive separator pairs can be adjacent.

The objective of the oGPVS problem is to minimize the total number of vertices in the separators. The constraint of the oGPVS problem is to maintain balance on the vertex part weights, where vertex part weight is defined as the sum of the weights of the part vertices.

The oGPVS problem and the permutation problem defined above is equivalent as follows: In the standard graph representation of a given symmetric matrix, each row/column is represented by a vertex and each symmetric nonzero pair is represented by an edge between the vertices corresponding to their row and column. Then, each diagonal block in the BDO form is represented by a vertex part and its left and right separators. That is, rows/columns of overlapping regions are represented by the vertices of separators and rows/columns of non-overlapping regions of diagonal blocks are represented by the vertices of vertex parts. Then minimizing the total separator size corresponds to minimizing the total overlap size and maintaining balance on the part weights relates to maintaining balance on the number of nonzeros of diagonal blocks where a weight that is equal to the number of nonzeros in the a row/column is assigned to a corresponding vertex.

We propose a graph partitioning algorithm to solve the oGPVS problem. We utilize recursive bipartitioning paradigm and fixed vertices in our algorithm. The main steps of our algorithm are as follows: First, we find a pseudo-peripheral vertex in the standard graph representation of the given matrix by the algorithm given in [4]. This algorithm also provides the level structure rooted at the found pseudo-peripheral vertex. We determine the length of that level structure and we terminate our algorithm if this length is smaller than $K-1$, where K is the desired number of blocks in the permuted BDO matrix (and equivalently the number of vertex parts). The reason for this termination is that the shortest path length between the left-most and the right-most ends of the final K -way partition is at least $K-1$ by selecting vertices only from the separators. If the level structure length is greater than or equal to $K-1$, then we set the pseudo-peripheral vertex as the left boundary of the graph and a furthest vertex to this vertex as the right boundary of the graph. Then we proceed with the following steps recursively: If K is equal to 2, then we fix the boundary vertices to the union of their corresponding side and the separator. In other words, left (right) boundary vertices cannot go to the right (left) in the resulting 2-way partition if K is equal to 2 (i.e. last-level recursive step). We need this boundary fixation for protecting the oGPVS partition structure. Then we find a 2-way GPVS of the

graph, i.e. left and right parts and a separator between them. Then we return this partitioning. If K is greater than 2, then we fix the vertices whose shortest path distance to the left (right) boundary is less than $K/2-1$ to the left (right) part. We need this fixation for guaranteeing that there exist two $K/2$ -way oGPVS partitions from left and right parts. After fixation, we find a 2-way GPVS of the graph. Then, we construct left and right subgraphs from left and right vertex parts returned by 2-way oGPVS for further recursive calls. We set the left (right) boundary of the left (right) subgraph as the left (right) boundary of the current graph. We set the vertices in the left (right) part that are adjacent to the separator vertices as the right (left) boundary of the left (right) subgraph. Then we recursively apply the same steps described above on the left and right subgraphs with $K/2$ as the new K value.

Currently, existing GPVS tools do not support fixed vertices. So we utilized the hypergraph partitioning (HP) based GPVS formulation proposed in [5] based on the existence of HP tools such as PaToH [6] that support fixed vertices.

We permute the given sparse square matrix with the resulting K -way oGPVS partition of its standard graph representation as follows: The rows and columns corresponding to the vertices of a vertex part are ordered after (before) the rows and columns corresponding to the vertices of its left (right) separator. In a dual manner, the rows and columns corresponding to the vertices of a separator are ordered after (before) the rows and columns corresponding to the vertices of its left (right) vertex part. The rows and columns corresponding to the vertices of a same separator or a same vertex part can be ordered arbitrarily.

3. Results Obtained

In our experiments, we measured the resulting total overlap size and load imbalance of the nonzeros in the diagonal blocks. We reported these results of our oGPVS algorithm in comparison to a baseline algorithm given in [3] that solves the same permutation problem. We tested these two algorithms for 4-, 8-, 16-, 32-, 64-, 128-, and 256-way BDO permutations for a wide range of matrices. We reported the results in geometric average for each K value.

Table 1. Performance comparison of the baseline and oGPVS algorithm in terms of total overlap size and load imbalance for different K values

K	Number of Matrices	Baseline Algorithm		oGPVS Algorithm		oGPVS/Baseline Overlap ratio
		Overlap %	Imbalance %	Overlap%	Imbalance%	
4	205	3.62	2.65	2.36	4.08	0.65
8	183	6.55	5.13	4.60	7.42	0.70
16	155	9.42	9.07	6.62	9.57	0.70
32	106	9.91	9.45	7.63	9.38	0.77
64	63	9.63	10.26	7.39	9.34	0.77
128	38	8.27	10.89	6.11	22.22	0.74
256	24	9.13	12.64	5.46	17.86	0.60

In Table 1, third and fifth columns show the ratio of the total number of rows/columns in the overlaps over the number of all rows/columns. The fourth and sixth columns of this table show the load imbalance which is calculated as $Z_{\max} / Z_{\text{avg}} - 1$, where Z_{\max} and Z_{avg} respectively denote the number of nonzeros in the maximally loaded diagonal block and the average load of diagonal blocks. The results in columns 3-7 are given as averages over matrices that both of these algorithms can produce valid BDO permutations. The number of such matrices is given in the second column for each specific K value. As seen in Table 1, for all of the tested K values, the oGPVS algorithm achieves a much smaller overlap size while producing a less balanced permutation. oGPVS algorithm produces permutations with 35%, 30%, 30%, 23%, 23%, 26%, and %40 smaller overlap size than the baseline algorithm for 4-, 8-, 16-, 32-, 64-, 128-, and 256-way BDO permutations, respectively.

4. Conclusion

We defined the problem of permuting a given sparse square matrix into block diagonal form with overlap. The objective in this problem is to minimize the total size of the overlaps that may be present between each two consecutive diagonal block pairs. We define ordered Graph Partitioning by Vertex Separator (oGPVS) problem as an equivalent problem to this permutation problem. We proposed a recursive graph partitioning algorithm that utilizes fixed vertices to solve the oGPVS problem. We compared the results of our proposed algorithm with the results of a baseline algorithm in terms of total overlap size and load imbalance. Our experiments conducted on a wide range of matrices showed that our algorithm achieves smaller overlap size than the baseline algorithm.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EUs 7th Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement no. RI-211528 and FP7-261557. The work is achieved using the PRACE Research Infrastructure resources [give the machine names, and the corresponding sites and countries].

References

1. G. A. A. Kahou, E. Kamgnia, and B. Philippe, Parallel implementation of an explicit formulation of the multiplicative Schwarz preconditioner, in CdROM Proceedings of IMACS05, 2005.
2. G. A. A. Kahou, E. Kamgnia, and B. Philippe, An explicit formulation of the multiplicative Schwarz preconditioner, *Applied Numerical Mathematics*, vol.: 57, pp.: 1197—1213, 2007.
3. G. A. A. Kahou, L. Grigori, and M. Sosonkina, A partitioning algorithm for block-diagonal matrices with overlap, *Parallel Computing*, vol.: 34, pp.: 332—344, 2008.
4. A. George and J.W. H. Liu, An implementation of a pseudoperipheral node finder, *ACM Trans. Math. Softw.* vol.: 5, pp.: 284—295, 1979.
5. U. V. Catalyurek, C. Aykanat, and E. Kayaaslan, Hypergraph partitioning-based fill-reducing ordering for symmetric matrices, *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, vol.: 33, pp.: 1996—2023, 2011.
6. U. V. Catalyurek and C. Aykanat, PaToH: A Multilevel Hypergraph Partitioning Tool, Version 3.0, Bilkent University, Department of Computer Engineering, Ankara, 06800 Turkey, 1999.